

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

Milestone MS5: 7 distinct language models adapted to the cardiology domain using EHR data

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Executive Summary

This report details the accomplishments in the Language Model (LM) Training and Evaluation work package as part of the DataTools4Heart project. The main objectives were to prepare, train, and evaluate state-of-the-art language models on cardiology-specific datasets in the languages of the consortium: English, Spanish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Swedish, and Czech. The tasks encompassed the collection, joining, and cleaning of datasets, establishing baseline performance metrics (both for perplexity and downstream NER tasks), and the development of a training pipeline. While key data acquisition and baseline evaluations have been successfully completed, the LM training run, detailed evaluations, and final hyperparameter adjustments are scheduled for upcoming phases. This milestone summarizes our progress and outlines the remaining steps to report the final experimental results.

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Acronyms

Electrocardiogram: ECG

Electronic Health Record: EHR

Graphics Processing Unit: GPU

High Performance Computing: HPC

Locality-Sensitive Hashing: LSH

Mare Nostrum 5: MN5

Milestone 5: MS5

Multilingual Parallel Clinical Text: Paraclite

Named Entity Recognition: NER

Natural Language Processing: NLP

Tensor Processing Unit: TPU

Work Package 3: WP3

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Preamble: Reason for extension request

The Milestone (MS) 5 submission delay stems from five interrelated factors that, together, have pushed back the team's timeline for delivering seven cardiology-adapted models:

1. **Synthetic clinical record generation:** Crafting privacy-preserving, expert-validated discharge summaries across seven sites couldn't be completed before mid-December 2024. These were necessary for the model perplexity evaluation.
2. **Multilingual data gaps:** Czech, Romanian and Swedish lacked sufficient clinical text, requiring time-intensive neural-translation and prompt-based augmentation.
3. **HPC migration:** Transitioning from MareNostrum 4 to MareNostrum 5 temporarily constrained GPU access for large-scale pretraining.
4. **Model-architecture review:** Evaluating newer architectures (DeBERTa, ClinicalMamba) delayed RoBERTa-style training to ensure state-of-the-art performance.
5. **Staff turnover:** Replacement of a key developer introduced a brief but impactful pause.

1 Introduction

The DataTools4Heart project seeks to build a comprehensive European Health Data Toolbox that enhances the interoperability, reusability, and privacy of cardiology-related data. By leveraging cutting-edge AI approaches and structured data models derived from electronic health record (EHR) resources, the consortium aims to support robust clinical decision support, large-scale research, and cross-border data sharing in cardiovascular medicine. Within this broader framework, Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on the development and evaluation of natural language processing (NLP) tools to be applied under a multilingual clinical language scenario, trying to ensure that NLP components can extract and normalize key clinical variables from clinical texts in each partner language.

Milestone 5 (MS5) is related to the outcome of Task T3.1, whose objective is basically to produce distinct language models—one per consortium language (English, Spanish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Swedish, and Czech)—and adapt them to the medical/clinical domain with particular coverage or focus on fine-tuning or adaptation to the cardiology-relevant content or domain. These domain-adapted models are intended to capture the specialized terminology, syntax, and stylistic conventions of medical content including cardiovascular medicine, thereby potentially improving performance on downstream tasks such as entity recognition (NER), information extraction, or other tasks. Achieving MS5 required four key steps:

- (1) Compiling a comprehensive multilingual resource inventory to determine the current status and potential reuse of existing resources of interest for the DT4H project.
- (2) Harvesting and preprocessing cardiology and biomedical datasets and corpora.
- (3) Conducting baseline evaluations and comparative analyses of existing clinical models.
- (4) Performing targeted domain adaptation via masked-language modeling on EHR datasets.

This report documents the approach to MS5, explaining the data sources and preprocessing methodologies (Section 2), the selection and configuration of base models for each language (Section 3), the training strategy employed on the MareNostrum 5 supercomputer (Section 4), and the evaluation protocols used to assess pseudo-perplexity and NER performance (Section 5).

By presenting both quantitative metrics and qualitative analyses, this milestone attempts to provide an account of the resulting accomplishments and outlines the remaining tasks required to finalize the CardioBERTa family of models for the DataTools4Heart consortium.

2 Methodology

The systematic approach followed to develop and evaluate the seven cardiology-adapted language models comprising Milestone 5 of the DataTools4Heart project is presented below in four successive phases. Each phase was designed to provide comprehensive coverage of data sourcing, model adaptation, and performance validation within the cardiology domain.

In the first phase, multilingual cardiology and biomedical corpora were acquired and preprocessed. Clinical texts, synthetic discharge summaries, journal articles, and professionally translated materials were gathered, and all texts were subjected to encoding normalization to resolve character inconsistencies. Deduplication was performed through exact string hashing and, where necessary, fuzzy clustering techniques such as locality-sensitive hashing (LSH). Domain-specific filtering was applied via regular expressions targeting cardiology terminology, supplemented by MeSH-based selection for biomedical abstracts.

In the second phase, appropriate transformer checkpoints were selected and configured for each target language. Encoder-only architectures from the RoBERTa and BERT families were preferred for their proven efficacy in masked-language modeling and sequence-labeling tasks. For English, the `allenai/biomed_roberta_base` model was adopted; for Spanish, `PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es`; for Czech, `ufal/robeczech-base`; and analogous domain-specialized or multilingual variants were chosen for Italian, Dutch, Romanian, and Swedish. Model hyperparameters—such as learning rate, optimizer settings, batch size, and sequence-length windowing—were standardized across languages to the extent permitted by each checkpoint's architecture.

When domain-specific pretrained language models are unavailable for a particular language or application, it is common practice to use large, general-purpose multilingual models as the backbone for clinical or biomedical NLP tasks. Models such as XLM-RoBERTa, NLLB, and Marian have been widely adopted due to their robust cross-lingual representations and coverage of many

languages, enabling transfer learning even in low-resource scenarios^{1 2}. This approach leverages the versatility of multilingual models, which are trained on vast and diverse corpora, to provide a strong foundation for downstream adaptation through fine-tuning on domain-specific data.

However, this strategy involves a clear trade-off. General-purpose multilingual models are not optimized for the specialized vocabulary, syntax, and semantics characteristic of clinical or biomedical texts. As a result, their downstream performance often lags behind that of domain-specific models, particularly in tasks that demand nuanced understanding of medical terminology or context³. For example, studies have shown that while multilingual models can be fine-tuned to achieve reasonable results, their general domain pretraining vocabulary may not sufficiently represent clinical language, potentially limiting accuracy in tasks such as named entity recognition or relation extraction. Furthermore, the lack of in-domain pre-training may result in models that are less sensitive to the unique linguistic patterns found in clinical documentation.

On the other hand, domain-specific models—when available—tend to outperform general models because they are pre-trained on large corpora of in-domain data, capturing the intricacies of medical language and concepts³. The main limitation is that such models require substantial amounts of data and computational resources, which are often unavailable for many languages or subdomains. In these cases, multilingual models offer a practical and scalable alternative, especially when combined with targeted fine-tuning and data cleaning strategies.

In the third phase, domain-adaptive pre-training was carried out on the MareNostrum 5 supercomputing infrastructure for the English, Spanish, Italian, Romanian, Czech and Swedish models. For the Dutch models we used the Google TPU research cloud for the publicly available data, and a single RTX 4000 ADA for the on-premise medical records. Data shards of approximately equal size were created to fit within runtime constraints, and a multi-epoch training pipeline was orchestrated. Each shard was processed sequentially: a base checkpoint was loaded, fine-tuned for five epochs on the shard using a masked-language modeling objective, and then checkpointed before proceeding to the next shard. This shard-based strategy ensured controlled exposure to up to several billion tokens of cardiology-specific text per model, while preserving reproducibility through containerized execution environments.

In the fourth phase, evaluation protocols were applied to quantify domain adaptation gains. Pseudo-perplexity was computed on the Multilingual Parallel Clinical Text (Paraclite) cardiology corpus using a sliding-window approach (window size 512 tokens and stride of 256) to measure masked-token recovery confidence. Token and word-level named entity recognition performance was assessed on the multilingual CardioCCC dataset following IOB⁴ tagging conventions; chunking strategies were employed to respect model context windows, and predictions were

¹ Qin, L., Chen, Q., Zhou, Y., Chen, Z., Li, Y., Liao, L., ... & Yu, P. S. (2025). A survey of multilingual large language models. *Patterns*, 6(1).

² Han, L., Gladkoff, S., Erofeev, G., Sorokina, I., Galiano, B., & Nenadic, G. (2024). Neural machine translation of clinical text: an empirical investigation into multilingual pre-trained language models and transfer-learning. *Frontiers in Digital Health*, 6, 1211564.

³ Shaitarova, A., Zagher, J., Lavelli, A., Krauthammer, M., & Rinaldi, F. (2023). Exploring the latest highlights in medical natural language processing across multiple languages: a survey. *Yearbook of medical informatics*, 32(01), 230-243.

⁴ Ramshaw, L. A., & Marcus, M. P. (1999). Text chunking using transformation-based learning. In *Natural language processing using very large corpora* (pp. 157-176). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.

realigned to original word spans for precision, recall, and F1 computation. Through these evaluations, the efficacy of each CardioBERTa model in capturing specialized cardiovascular terminology and supporting downstream clinical NLP tasks was studied.

Development of Cardiology-Specific Language Model

Figure 1. Methodology used for model training. This example shows the settings for the Spanish model.

2.1 Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

Selecting and gathering the right data is a crucial part of training an effective language model. However, the availability of high-quality datasets can vary greatly between languages. For example, while English has a vast number of openly available resources, languages like Czech and Romanian often have far fewer options. This difference means tailored strategies had to be used for each language.

Data sources can be categorised into three main domains: general, biomedical/clinical, and cardiology-specific. The primary focus is on cardiology data, ensuring the language model is finely tuned to this field. Given the scarcity of this type of data or that in general it is mixed with other clinical documents, in order to have enough data for a consistent training it was necessary to look to biomedical and clinical sources, and only add general domain data if necessary.

Looking at where the data comes from, there are three key sources:

1. **Clinical records:** These are anonymized health records and patient histories that offer genuine insights into clinical language, though they must be handled with strict privacy controls.

2. **Openly Available and Curated Datasets:** These are trusted, pre-vetted resources that provide a reliable foundation for our models, especially in the biomedical and clinical areas.
3. **Text from Academic Journals and Machine-Translated Content:** This includes text extracted from medical journals including cardiology-specific ones and content that has been translated using machine translation systems. While these sources add valuable content, they also require careful quality checks to ensure accuracy and maintain the specialized language of the field.

By combining these complementary approaches, it is possible to create a diverse multilingual data collection to be further used for training of general clinical language models, but also enriched for cardiology language and domain content.

2.1.1 Data Cleaning

The data cleaning process was designed to be straightforward yet effective. This process started by eliminating problematic characters that often arise from encoding issues, which is especially common when extracting text from PDFs. To ensure each document was unique, deduplication was performed using strict matching techniques like string hashing. For sources where the quality was lower due to extraction challenges (typically with PDF parsing), it was applied fuzzy deduplication methods such as Locality-Sensitive Hashing (LSH)⁵ and clustering.

2.1.2 Data Selection

Finding isolated cardiology data can be challenging because it rarely exists as a standalone dataset. Instead, it is often embedded within larger text repositories. For example, resources like SciELO⁶ in Spanish and English contain a mix of articles, some of which are related to cardiology. To extract these, regular expressions and keyword filtering were applied to magazine names, descriptions, and publisher information. One pattern we employed was:

```
(?i)\b(?:cardio(?:log(?:y|ía))?|heart|coronary|vascular)\b
```

If any match was found, the corresponding article was selected. A similar approach was used to extract cardiology-related content from the MIMIC clinical notes. Additionally, for PubMed, all MeSH terms⁷ related to cardiovascular disease and its subcategories were extracted.

⁵ Rajaraman, A., & Ullman, J. D. (2010). Mining of massive datasets (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press.

⁶ Packer, A. L., Prat, A. M., Luccisano, A., Montanari, F., Santos, S., & Meneghini, R. (2006). El modelo SciELO de publicación científica de calidad en acceso abierto. Edición electrónica, bibliotecas virtuales y portales para las ciencias sociales en América Latina y El Caribe, 191-208.

⁷ Leydesdorff, L., Comins, J. A., Sorensen, A. A., Bornmann, L., & Hellsten, I. (2016). Cited references and Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) as two different knowledge representations: clustering and mappings at the paper level. *Scientometrics*, 109(3), 2077-2091.

2.1.3 Amount of data

To measure the amount of data collected, it was considered that a word is a sequence of alphanumeric characters. In Table 1, the number of words in the retrieved documents is displayed by domain.

Table 1: Number of words per language in the dataset in millions

Language	Cardiology	Biomedical	General
English	771	8	163
Spanish	207	3,578	0
Swedish	143	2,460	0
Czech	150	2,330	403
Italian	266	4,562	0
Romanian	184	4,211	0
Dutch	1,400	4,073	0

Approximately 2,000 million words of the Biomedical data for each language come from machine translated English PubMed abstracts provided by Translated. All the translations have been carried out using ModernMT⁸.

In the case of English, the original weights of the allenai/biomed_roberta_base model correspond to RoBERTa, which was initially pretrained on a large, diverse English corpus covering a wide range of topics⁹. Subsequently, this model underwent continual pretraining on the Semantic Scholar Open Research Corpus, which contains millions of biomedical research articles¹⁰. As a result, it is highly likely that the model has already been exposed to a substantial amount of biomedical literature, including articles relevant to the cardiology domain. Therefore, for domain adaptation to cardiology, the main focus has been put exclusively on cardiology-specific texts to ensure that the adaptation process targets the nuances and terminology unique to this field. This approach also explains why the total amount of biomedical data used for English is smaller compared to other languages and additional efforts were concentrated on fine-tuning with high-quality, domain-specific data.

⁸ Germann, U., Barbu, E., Bentivogli, L., Bertoldi, N., Bogoychev, N., Buck, C., ... & Trombetti, M. (2016). Modern MT: A New Open-Source Machine Translation Platform for the Translation Industry. *Baltic Journal of Modern Computing*, 4(2).

⁹ Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2019). Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*.

¹⁰ Lo, K., Wang, L. L., Neumann, M., Kinney, R., & Weld, D. S. (2019). S2ORC: The semantic scholar open research corpus. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.02782*.

2.2 Model Selection for Domain Adaptation

Encoder-only models like BERT¹¹, RoBERTa¹², and XLM-RoBERTa¹³ have become standard tools in natural language processing for tasks such as text classification and named entity recognition. BERT was one of the first models to learn from both the left and right context of a word, which greatly improved the understanding of language. Building on this, RoBERTa improved the training process by using more data and optimizing training steps, resulting in models that often perform better in practice. XLM-RoBERTa extends these ideas to work across multiple languages, making it a strong option when dealing with diverse language resources.

For this project, RoBERTa is especially interesting because it not only shows strong performance in real-world tasks, but there are also many high-quality, pre-trained RoBERTa models available for nearly every target language we work with. This makes it easier to adapt the models to our specific needs without having to train from scratch, which saves both time and computational resources. Using these models allowed us to start with a solid foundation and then fine-tune them for the specialized language found in clinical texts.

For **English**, the selected model was *allenai/biomed_roberta_base* model¹⁴, a RoBERTa variant specifically pre-trained on a large corpus of biomedical literature and clinical texts. More concretely, 2.68 million scientific papers from the Semantic Scholar corpus via continued pretraining. This amounts to 7.55B tokens and 47 GB of data. This specialized training helps the model to better understand medical terminology and the context in which it is used, making it particularly effective for biomedical natural language processing tasks such as named entity recognition and text classification. By leveraging this domain-specific knowledge, this project benefits from improved accuracy and a strong foundation for further fine-tuning on clinical data.

In the case of **Spanish**, *PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es*¹⁵ is the chosen model. The training corpus combined several Spanish biomedical datasets, gathered from public sources and crawlers, with a real-world clinical corpus derived from over 278,000 clinical documents and notes. To maintain high quality while preserving the unique characteristics of clinical language, a cleaning pipeline consisting of data parsing, sentence splitting, language detection, filtering of ill-formed sentences, deduplication, and preservation of original document boundaries was applied exclusively to the biomedical data before it was merged with the unaltered

¹¹ Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019, June). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies, volume 1 (long and short papers) (pp. 4171-4186).

¹² Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2019). Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692.

¹³ Conneau, A., Khandelwal, K., Goyal, N., Chaudhary, V., Wenzek, G., Guzmán, F., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2019). Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale. arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.02116.

¹⁴ Gururangan, S., Marasović, A., Swayamdipta, S., Lo, K., Beltagy, I., Downey, D., & Smith, N. A. (2020). Don't stop pretraining: Adapt language models to domains and tasks. arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.10964.

¹⁵ Carrino, C. P., Armengol-Estapé, J., Bonet, O. D. G., Gutiérrez-Fandiño, A., Gonzalez-Agirre, A., Krallinger, M., & Villegas, M. (2021). Spanish biomedical crawled corpus: A large, diverse dataset for Spanish biomedical language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.07765.

clinical corpus. This process resulted in a medium-sized Spanish biomedical-clinical corpus of over 1 billion tokens.

In languages with more limited resources, such as **Czech**, the candidate was ufal/robeczech-base¹⁶ model. Although trained on more general data, its RoBERTa architecture demonstrates considerable effectiveness in lower-resource environments, providing a solid base for further domain-specific adaptation. It was originally trained on a collection of publicly available Czech texts that together total 4,917 million tokens. The dataset includes SYN v4, a contemporary Czech corpus with 4,188 million tokens; Czes, a collection of newspaper and magazine articles with 432 million tokens; documents from the Czech web corpus W2C contributing 16 million tokens; and plain texts from the Czech Wikipedia dump adding 123 million tokens.

Similarly, the CLTL/MedRoBERTa.nl model¹⁷, with 125 million parameters, serves the **Dutch** biomedical domain, benefiting from the robust training regimen inherent to the RoBERTa framework. It was trained with nearly 10 million anonymized hospital notes from the Amsterdam University Medical Centres.

For **Italian**, the IVN-RIN/bioBIT model¹⁸ is used. BioBIT is a biomedical language model built on the BERT architecture, derived from the Italian XXL BERT checkpoint. It has been pretrained on an extensive corpus that combines a recent Wikipedia dump with various texts from the OPUS and OSCAR corpora, totaling 81 GB of data and 13 billion tokens. Following the pretraining approach outlined in the BioBERT paper, BioBIT uses a combination of masked language modeling (MLM) and next sentence prediction (NSP) as its training objectives. To address the limited availability of native Italian biomedical literature, machine translation was used to generate an Italian biomedical corpus from PubMed abstracts. This large-scale training and domain adaptation enable BioBIT to perform effectively on downstream tasks such as Named Entity Recognition, extractive Question Answering, and Relation Extraction in the biomedical field.

For **Romanian**, no domain-specific pretrained model was available, so XLM-RoBERTa model was selected as the backbone. XLM-RoBERTa is a robust, multilingual model trained on a large corpus covering over 100 languages, including Romanian. Its extensive training and strong cross-lingual representations make it an effective choice for tasks in the biomedical and clinical domains, where specialized models for Romanian remain scarce. This approach allows us to leverage the model's versatility and fine-tune it for our specific Romanian language tasks.

¹⁶ Straka, M., Náplava, J., Straková, J., & Samuel, D. (2021). RobeCzech: Czech RoBERTa, a monolingual contextualized language representation model. In Text, Speech, and Dialogue: 24th International Conference, TSD 2021, Olomouc, Czech Republic, September 6–9, 2021, Proceedings 24 (pp. 197-209). Springer International Publishing.

¹⁷ Verkijk, S., & Vossen, P. (2021, December). MedRoBERTa.nl: a language model for Dutch electronic health records. In Computational Linguistics in the Netherlands (Vol. 11, pp. 141-159). Computational Linguistics in the Netherlands.

¹⁸ Buonocore, T. M., Crema, C., Redolfi, A., Bellazzi, R., & Parimbelli, E. (2023). Localizing in-domain adaptation of transformer-based biomedical language models. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 144, 104431.

Lastly, for **Swedish**, we use a suite of models developed by the National Library of Sweden and KBLab. The base model, KB/bert-base-swedish-cased¹⁹, is built on the BERT architecture and was pretrained on approximately 15-20GB of text from diverse sources, including books, news, government publications, Swedish Wikipedia, and internet forums, totaling around 200 million sentences and 3 billion tokens.

Table 2: Base models selected for each language.

Language	Base Model	Parameters	Type	Domain
English	allenai/biomed_roberta_base	125M	RoBERTa	Biomedical
Spanish	PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es	125M	RoBERTa	Biomedical
Swedish	KB/bert-base-swedish-cased	110M	BERT	General
Czech	ufal/robeczech-base	125M	RoBERTa	General
Italian	IVN-RIN/bioBIT	110M	BERT	Biomedical
Romanian	FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-base	270M	XLM-RoBERTa	General
Dutch	CLTL/MedRoBERTa.nl	125M	RoBERTa	Biomedical

2.3 Model Pre-training

Each model in the CardioBERTa family was trained using a central PyTorch²⁰-based script, tailored to run efficiently on the MareNostrum 5 (MN5) infrastructure. The standard execution configuration involved eight nodes of the accelerated partition, each with four NVIDIA H100²¹ GPUs (32 GPUs total), coordinated using *torchrun* library for distributed training. The script, run within a Singularity²² container to ensure reproducibility, used *Hugging Face's Transformers*²³ library to load the language-specific base models. The training cycle was managed using *Transformers' Trainer* class for the sake of simplicity and reproducibility.

The training strategy adopted was specific to each target language. Instead of continuous training on a single model, a different pre-trained base model was selected *ad-hoc* for each language (explained in the Methodology Section). Due to the large volume of data, it was necessary to be splitted into multiple smaller batches to facilitate job management and avoid exceeding runtime limits in MN5. Training for a specific language processed sequentially across these shards:

¹⁹ Malmsten, M., Börjeson, L., & Haffenden, C. (2020). Playing with Words at the National Library of Sweden--Making a Swedish BERT. arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.01658.

²⁰ Paszke, A. (2019). Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library. arXiv preprint arXiv:1912.01703.

²¹ Choquette, J. (2023). Nvidia hopper h100 gpu: Scaling performance. IEEE Micro, 43(3), 9-17.

²² Kurtzer, G. M., Sochat, V., & Bauer, M. W. (2017). Singularity: Scientific containers for mobility of compute. PloS one, 12(5), e0177459.

²³ Wolf, T., Debut, L., Sanh, V., Chaumond, J., Delangue, C., Moi, A., ... & Rush, A. M. (2020, October). Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing. In Proceedings of the 2020 conference on empirical methods in natural language processing: system demonstrations (pp. 38-45).

1. The base model for the language was loaded
2. It was trained on the first data shard for 5 epochs applying the defined hyperparameters and an intermediate checkpoint was saved.
3. This checkpoint was then loaded as a starting point for training on the second shard (again, 5 epochs with the same hyperparameters)

This process was repeated over all data shards until the final CardioBERTa model for that specific language was obtained.

The management of this sequence of jobs (one job per shard for each language) was orchestrated using the internal *Cosmos* library—developed by the BSC team—which allowed each training step to be triggered by passing the path of the corresponding data shard and the previous model's checkpoint as parameters to the script.

Training hyperparameters were 5 epochs with a batch size of 16 for each GPU, using AdamW optimizer with a decay rate of 1E-3, learning rate with peak values of 1E-4 and 5E-4 and a linear warmup of 10% of the total iterations together with linear decay. The selected data chunking method was a sliding window per document with a size of 512 and a stride of 256 in order to respect the maximum sequence length of RoBERTa models while ensuring to capture the context in every case. This configuration was used throughout the five training epochs within each shard, ensuring a progressive and controlled adaptation of the language-specific base model to the biomedical/cardiological domain as it processed successive data shards.

Figure 2. Diagram of Training using MareNostrum 5.

2.4 Evaluation of Language Models

2.4.1 Pseudo-perplexity

Pseudo-perplexity²⁴ is an evaluation metric tailored for masked language models like RoBERTa, where it measures how well the model predicts tokens that have been masked out, effectively serving as a proxy for traditional perplexity. It measures a model's familiarity with domain-specific language and its ability to maintain coherence in clinical narratives. Empirical studies have shown that pseudo-perplexity and perplexity metrics exhibit some of the highest correlations with human judgments of text coherence, with statistically significant Spearman correlation coefficients as high as -0.45 for pseudo-perplexity across various language models and datasets²⁵. This means that models with lower pseudo-perplexity scores are more likely to produce outputs that human experts judge as coherent and contextually appropriate, which is critical in clinical settings where accuracy and clarity are crucial.

In this work, pseudo-perplexity is calculated on the Multilingual PARallel CLInical TExt (Paraclite), a multilingual parallel corpus of synthetic cardiovascular clinical texts, and it is an output of the Task 3.2 of the DataTools4Heart project. This dataset, comprising approximately 350,000 words evenly distributed across seven languages, was created by clinicians who crafted realistic clinical reports, mimicking outpatient, inpatient, and emergency department narratives, in their native language and then professionally translated these texts into six additional languages. Available in both document-aligned and segment-aligned views, Paraclite is enriched with detailed metadata such as clinical annotations for symptoms, heart disorders, and comorbidities, as well as contextual clarifications of domain-specific terminology. Designed primarily for research in natural language processing and medical AI, it supports tasks like machine translation, automated medical coding, and cross-lingual information retrieval, all while ensuring data privacy through the use of fictional patient data.

Provided that each of the documents are split into segments and translated to the rest of languages in the consortium as shown in Figure 3, the computation of pseudo-perplexity started with first concatenating all segments of the same document into a single sequence and then tokenizing it using the RoBERTa tokenizer. In order to do so, a sliding window approach similar to the one performed for the training step was used to chunk the sequence, allowing to compute the score for each chunk based on the conditional probability of each masked token given its context. Once again, given that for all of the models the maximum sequence length is 512 tokens, the size of the window has been set to that amount and, to allow seeing the same tokens in different contexts, the stride is set to 256 tokens. The overall performance is determined by aggregating the negative log-likelihood and perplexity scores from these chunks, providing a robust measure of the model's ability to represent and predict the language in our corpus.

²⁴ Salazar, J., Liang, D., Nguyen, T. Q., & Kirchhoff, K. (2019). Masked language model scoring. arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.14659.

²⁵ Sartor, M., Dell'Orletta, F., & Venturi, G. (2024). Coherence Evaluation in Italian Language Models. In Proceedings of the Eighth Workshop on Natural Language for Artificial Intelligence (NL4AI 2024) co-located with 23th International Conference of the Italian Association for Artificial Intelligence (AI* IA 2024), CEUR-WS. org.

src	lang	doc_name	seg	id	split	en	it	nl	cs	es	ro	sv	
en	en	patient_16.txt	0	test		Review Date 04/04/2021	Data Revisione 04/04/2021	Beoordelingsdatum 04-04-2021	Datum revize 4. 4. 2021	Fecha de revisión 04/04/2021	Data consultului 04.04.2021	GRSkningsdatum 2021	
en	en	patient_16.txt	1	test		Dear General Practitioner	Gentile medico di medicina	Geachte huisarts	Vážení praktický lékař,	Estimado médico general,	Stimate medic generalist,	Bästa allmänläkare	
en	en	patient_16.txt	2	test		Re: James Stroud, DOB: 01/03/6	Oggetto: James Stroud, data:	Betreff: James Stroud, geb. datum:	Předmět: James Stroud, d	Asunto: James Stroud, fecha de	Referitor: la James Stroud, da	Ängående: James Strou	
en	en	patient_16.txt	3	test		Thank you for referring James Str	La ringraziamo per aver invia	Bedankt voor het verwijzen van J	děkujeme za odesláni Jan	Gracias por remitir a James Str	Vă mulțumim că i-ați făcut trim	Tack for att du hänvisade	
en	en	patient_16.txt	4	test		He is a 61 year old gentleman w	L paziente è un uomo di 61	Hij is een 61-jarige heer met een	Ude o 61letého muže s kor	Es un caballero de 61 años con	Este un domn de 61 de ani cu	Han är en 61-årig gentleman	
en	en	patient_16.txt	5	test		He is an active smoker.	Fumatore attivo.	Hij is een actieve roker.	Je aktivním kuřákem.	Es fumador activo.	Este un fumător activ.	Han är en aktiv rökare.	
en	en	patient_16.txt	6	test		He reports a worsening of his che	Riferisce un peggioramento	Hij meldt een verslechtering van	Od své poslední návštěvy	Refiere un empeoramiento de	Reportează o agravare a dure	Han rapporterar om en ft	
en	en	patient_16.txt	7	test		He describes the pain as tight, sh	Descrive il dolore come oppr	Hij beschrijft de pijn als drukkend	Bolest popisuje jako svíra	Describe el dolor como opresiv	Descrie durerea ca o senza	Han beskriver smärtan s	
en	en	patient_16.txt	8	test		The pain is exacerbated by phys	Il dolore è aggravato dall'att	De pijn wordt erger tijdens fysiek	Bolest se zhoršuje s fyzick	El dolor se agrava con el activ	Durerea este exacerbată de	Smrátna förvärras av fys	
en	en	patient_16.txt	9	test		This is reducing his ability to wal	Cio limita la sua capacità di	Daar toe is hij minder in staat om	Tim se snižuje jeho schop	Esto le reduce su capacidad p	Durerea îi reduce capacitate	Detta minskar hans förm	
en	en	patient_16.txt	10	test		He continues to smoke 10-15 cig	Continua a fumare 10-15 sig	Hij blijft 10-15 sigareten per dag	Nadále kouří 10-15 cigare	Sigue fumando de 10 a 15 cig	Continuă să fumeze câte 10-	Han fortsätter att röka 10	
en	en	patient_16.txt	11	test		Current Medications:	Terapie in corso:	Huidige medicatie:	Současné léky:	Medicación actual:	Medicația actuală:	Aktuella mediciner:	
en	en	patient_16.txt	12	test		Apixaban	Apixaban	Apixaban	Apixaban	Apixaban	Apixaban	Apixaban	
en	en	patient_16.txt	13	test		Bisoprolol 3.75mg once daily	Bisoprololo 3,75mg QD	Bisoprolol 3,75 mg eenmaal daa	Bisoprolol 3,75 mg jednou	Bisoprolol 3,75 mg una vez al	Bisoprolol 3,75 mg 1 x zi	Bisoprolol 3,75 mg en g	
en	en	patient_16.txt	14	test		Atorvastatin 20mg once daily	Atorvastatina 20 mg QD	Atorvastatin 20 mg eenmaal daa	Atorvastatin 20 mg jednou	Atorvastatin 20 mg una vez al	Atorvastatină 20 mg 1 x zi	Atorvastatin 20 mg en g	
en	en	patient_16.txt	15	test		Metformin 500mg once daily	Metformina 500 mg QD	Metformine 500 mg eenmaal daa	Metformin 500 mg jednou	Metformina 500 mg una vez al	Metformină 500 mg 1 x zi	Metformin 500 mg en g	
en	en	patient_16.txt	16	test		Sitagliptin 50mg once daily	Sitagliptin 50 mg QD	Sitagliptine 50 mg eenmaal daa	Sitagliptin 50 mg jednou	Sitagliptina 50 mg una vez al	Sitagliptin 50 mg 1 x zi	Sitagliptin 50 mg en g	
en	en	patient_16.txt	17	test		Gliclazide 40mg once daily	Gliclazide 40 mg QD	Gliclazide 40 mg eenmaal daa	Gliclazid 40 mg jednou	Gliclazida 40 mg una vez al	Gliclazidă 40 mg 1 x zi	Gliclazid 40 mg en g	
en	en	patient_16.txt	18	test		Cyanocobalamin 50mcg once da	Cianocobalamina 50mcg QD	Cyanocobalamine 50 mcg eenma	Kyanokobalamin 50 µg jed	Cianocobalamina 50 mcg una	Cianocobalamină 50 µg 1 x zi	Cyanocobalamin 50 µg	
en	en	patient_16.txt	19	test		Ferrous Fumarate 210mg twice	Fumarato Ferroso 210mg B	Ferroumlumaraat 210 mg tweemaal	Ferrum(II)-fumarát 210 mg	Fumarato ferroso 210 mg dos	Fumarato feros 210 mg 1 x zi	Jämfumarat 210 mg två	
en	en	patient_16.txt	20	test		Cardiac MRI Report: A recent ca	Referto di RM cardiaca: una	Cardio-MRI verslag: een recente	Zpráva z MR srdce: Nedáv	Informe de RM cardiaca: una	Raport de RMN cardiac: Un	Hjärt-MR-rapport: En ny	
en	en	patient_16.txt	21	test		The left ventricular ejection fract	La frazione di eiezione ventric	Behouden linkerventriek-ejectie	Ejekční frakce levé komory	La fracción de eyección del ven	Fracția de eiecție a ventricul	Vänster ventrikulär ejekt	
en	en	patient_16.txt	22	test		There was no evidence of ongo	Nessuna evidenza di perica	Er waren geen tekenen van aan	Nebýly zjištěny žádné zn	No hubo evidencia de pericard	Nu s-au constatat semne de	Deft finns inga tecken p	
en	en	patient_16.txt	23	test		His ECG showed normal sinus	l'ECG mostrava un ritmo sin	Zijn ECG toonde een normaal	EkG ukázalo normální sin	ECG mostro un ritmo sinus	Rezultatele EKG au arătat un	Intytat	
en	en	patient_16.txt	24	test		This is unchanged from his last	Questo che resta invariato	Dit is onveranderd ten opzichte	To se od poslední kontroly	Su estado no ha cambiado des	Constatărilor nu s-au schim	Detta är oförändrad från	
en	en	patient_16.txt	25	test		His heart rate was 85 this mornin	Stamattina la frequenza card	Zijn hartslagfrequentie was van	Dnes ráno měl tepovou fre	Su ritmo cardíaco en reposo	er	În această dimineață, ritmul	Hans hjärtfrekvens var 8
en	en	patient_16.txt	26	test		I have added a long acting nitrate	Ho aggiunto un nitrato a lung	Ik heb een langwerkend nitraat	Do jeho medikace jsem př	He añadido un nitrato de acci	Am adăugat la schema de tra	Jag har tillsatt ett långve	
en	en	patient_16.txt	27	test		If he is in ongoing pain, please	In caso di dolore persistente	Als hij voortdurend pijn heeft,	ove	Pokud bude mít přetrvávaj	Si el dolor continúa, considere	Daacă va avea dureri persiste	Om han har pågående s
en	en	patient_16.txt	28	test		I note his last HbA1c on your sy	Segnaio che la sua ultima	Ik merk op dat zijn laatste	HbA1c	Všiml jsem si, že jeho pos	Observo que su última HbA1c	Menționez că ultima valoare	Jag noterar att hans sen
en	en	patient_16.txt	29	test		I have counselled him again on	Gi ho nuovamente illustrato	Ik heb hem opnieuw gewezen	o	Znovu jsem mu poskytl por	Le he aconsejado de nuevo so	Am oferit din nou consiliere	Jag har gett honom råd i
en	en	patient_16.txt	30	test		Impression	Valutazione clinica	Indruk	Dojem	Impresión diagnóstica	Observație clinică	Intytat	
en	en	patient_16.txt	31	test		No evidence of pericarditis.	Non sono state riscontrate	Geen aanwijzingen voor pericard	Žádné známky perikarditid	Sin evidencia de pericarditis.	Nu sunt prezente semne de	Intytat tecken på perikardi	
en	en	patient_16.txt	32	test		Ongoing symptomatic ischaemic	Cardiopatia ischemica sintom	Anhoudende symptomatische	Přetrvávající symptomatick	Cardiopatía isquémica sintom	Boală cardiacă ischemică sim	Pågående symptomatisk i	
en	en	patient_16.txt	33	test		Plan	Piano terapeutico	Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan	
en	en	patient_16.txt	34	test		Increase Bisoprolol to 5mg once	Aumentare il bisoprololo a 5	Verhoog Bisoprolol tot 5 mg een	Zvýšit dávku bisoprololu	Aumentar el bisoprolol a 5 mg	Creșterea dozei de bisoprolol	Öka bisoprolol till 5 mg	
en	en	patient_16.txt	35	test		Add Isosorbide Mononitrate 30m	Aggiungere Isosorbide Mono	Voeg eenmaal daags 30 mg isos	Přidat isosorbid-mononitr	Añadir 30 mg de mononitrato	Adăugarea de izosorbid mon	Tillsätt isosorbidmononit	
en	en	patient_16.txt	36	test		Add Empagliflozin 10MG OD.	Aggiungere Empagliflozin 1	Voeg Empagliflozin 10 mg een	Přidat empagliflozin 10 mg	Añadir empagliflozin 10 mg	Adăugarea de empagliflozin	Tillsätt empagliflozin 10	
en	en	patient_16.txt	37	test		Add Ivabradine if pain recurs.	Aggiungere ivabradina se il	Voeg ivabradine toe als de pijn	Přidat ivabradin, pokud se	Añadir ivabradina si el dolor	Adăugarea de ivabradină	Tillsätt ivabradin om sm	

Figure 3. Source word distribution by language in Paraclite dataset.

When a model is trained on data from the cardiology domain, it becomes familiar with the specific vocabulary, syntax, and stylistic patterns common to that field. As a result, when this model is evaluated on the Paraclite dataset, which contains similar cardiology-related texts, the pseudo-perplexity score should be lower compared to a model trained on more general data. This lower score indicates that the model is more confident and accurate in predicting the masked tokens, reflecting its enhanced ability to understand and represent cardiology-specific language.

Regarding the test set, Paraclite is a multilingual parallel corpus of synthetic cardiovascular clinical texts, and it is an output of the Task 3.2 of the DataTools4Heart project. This dataset, comprising approximately 350,000 words evenly distributed across seven languages (see Figure 4), was created by clinicians who crafted realistic clinical reports, mimicking outpatient, inpatient, and emergency department narratives, in their native language and then professionally translated these texts into six additional languages. Available in both document-aligned and segment-aligned views, Paraclite is enriched with detailed metadata such as clinical annotations for symptoms, heart disorders, and comorbidities, as well as contextual clarifications of domain-specific terminology. Designed primarily for research in natural language processing and medical AI, it supports tasks like machine translation, automated medical coding, and cross-lingual information retrieval, all while ensuring data privacy through the use of fictional patient data.

Figure 4. Source word distribution by language in Paraclite dataset.

2.4.2 Downstream Task. Named Entity Recognition.

In the context of the DataTools4Heart project, CardioCCC²⁶ corpus was created to serve as a benchmark for evaluating our language models on downstream tasks. CardioCCC is a multilingual clinical dataset that originated from a manually annotated Gold Standard corpus in Spanish, which was then translated into six additional languages and rigorously validated by clinical experts. Structured in both document-aligned and segment-aligned formats, the corpus features comprehensive annotations for key clinical labels such as disease, medication, procedure, and symptoms.

2.4.2.1 Data Preparation

In CardioCCC the entities present in a document are labeled by mention spans, containing the text, their starting and ending positions in the text and their class (medication, disease, symptom and procedure). It was decided to convert entity spans to tags following the Inside–outside–beginning (IOB)²⁷ format, specifically IOB2²⁸, due to several reasons: it provides explicit boundary clarity, it aligns seamlessly with sequence labeling models, and it ensures interoperability and ease of deployment across various NLP tools and systems due to its widespread standardization.

²⁶ Lima-López S, Farré-Maduell E, Rodríguez-Miret J, Rodríguez-Ortega M, Lilli L, Lenkiewicz J, Ceroni G, Kossoff J, Shah A, Nentidis A, Krithara A. Overview of multicardioner task at biosq 2024 on medical speciality and language adaptation of clinical ner systems for spanish, english and italian. CLEF Working Notes. 2024

²⁷ Ramshaw, L., & Marcus, M. (1995). Text Chunking using Transformation-Based Learning. In Third Workshop on Very Large Corpora.

²⁸ Tjong Kim Sang, E., & Veenstra, J. (1999). Representing Text Chunks. In Ninth Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics (pp. 173–179). Association for Computational Linguistics.

Spans were converted to IOB tags by chunking the documents using the SpaCy²⁹ word tokenizer and assigned to each word the proper IOB tag.

Document length posed a further challenge, as transformer encoder-based language models impose a fixed token-context window. To prevent loss of context or the splitting of entity spans, a cascade splitting strategy was implemented: texts were successively divided into paragraphs, lines, and sentences. At each splitting step, the tokenized segment was tested for compatibility with the model's maximum sequence length; segments fitting within the limit were retained as chunks, while longer segments were further subdivided. This procedure produced model-compatible chunks—each no longer than a line segment—and chunk-level predictions were concatenated to yield document-level outputs.

Subword tokenization necessitated a strategy for mapping token-level predictions back to words, since single words can be split into multiple tokens. To maintain entity consistency, each token inherited the label of the word-initial token of its parent word.

2.4.2.2 Training

Token-classification models were trained on the CardioCCC training set under a multilabel, multiclass framework—reflecting the possibility of multiple tags per word and IOB2 tagging classes (B, I, O). Optimization was carried out with Adam to minimize mean cross-entropy loss per label. Training proceeded until validation-loss convergence or a maximum of 30 epochs, with batch sizes ranging from 8 to 64 and learning rates between 2E-5 and 1E-4, depending on the base model.

2.4.2.3 Evaluation

For evaluation, token-level predictions were realigned to word-level tags by pooling subword token probabilities: the average probability across a word's tokens was computed, and the class with the highest mean probability was selected. Precision, recall, and F1 scores were then calculated on the CardioCCC test set using the seqeval³⁰ framework. Both token-level and word-level metrics were reported, with macro-averages presented to account for class imbalance.

3 Results

Across the seven languages, pseudo-perplexity was used to assess how well each model predicts masked cardiology terms: lower values indicate a tighter fit to the domain. Notable reductions were observed for English (12.01 to 6.87, -42.8 %), Spanish (26.33 to 2.25, -91.5 %), Czech (10.25 to 5.27, -48.6 %), and Romanian (67.43 to 11.94, -82.3 %). These drops

²⁹ Honnibal, M. (2017). spaCy 2: Natural language understanding with Bloom embeddings, convolutional neural networks and incremental parsing. (No Title).

³⁰ Hiroki Nakayama. (2018). seqeval: A Python framework for sequence labeling evaluation.

reflect a substantial increase in the models' confidence when encountering domain-specific vocabulary caused by the fact of both base models being original in general domain and multilingual in the case of Romanian. In contrast, Swedish, Italian, and Dutch exhibited perplexity increases (+15.9 %, +28.8 %, +68.0 % respectively), indicating that either their base checkpoints already contained considerable cardiology content or that mismatches between the new EHR data and pre-existing training distributions hindered further perplexity gains.

Table 3: Pseudo-perplexity comparison

Language	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Variation
English	12.01	6.87	-0.4280
Spanish	26.33	2.25	-0.9145
Swedish	4.79	5.55	0.1594
Czech	10.25	5.27	-0.4859
Italian	5.28	6.80	0.2879
Romanian	67.43	11.94	-0.8229
Dutch	3.98	6.7	0.68

Token-level NER performance was generally preserved or modestly enhanced by domain adaptation. English saw its macro-F1 score rise from 0.80 to 0.83, driven by simultaneous improvements in recall (0.74 to 0.77) and precision (0.89 to 0.90). Swedish also recorded a +0.02 F1 gain (0.77 to 0.79), while Romanian and Dutch posted smaller increases of +0.01 and +0.02 F1, respectively. Spanish and Italian held steady at 0.88 and 0.79, demonstrating that strong baseline tagging was maintained. Czech's F1 score remained at 0.81 despite a slight recall decrease (0.81 to 0.79) offset by a precision gain (0.82 to 0.85). Overall, these results show that even in cases where perplexity did not improve, the models retained—or slightly boosted—their capacity to identify clinical entity spans at the subword level.

Table 4: NER performance comparison (token level). All metrics are macro.

Language	F1 Score	F1 Score	Recall	Recall	Precision	Precision
	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model
English	0.80	0.83	0.74	0.77	0.89	0.90
Spanish	0.88	0.88	0.86	0.87	0.91	0.91
Swedish	0.77	0.79	0.74	0.76	0.82	0.83
Czech	0.81	0.81	0.81	0.79	0.82	0.85
Italian	0.79	0.79	0.78	0.77	0.79	0.80
Romanian	0.80	0.81	0.77	0.82	0.83	0.81

Language	F1 Score	F1 Score	Recall	Recall	Precision	Precision
	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model
Dutch	0.80	0.82	0.79	0.82	0.81	0.82

When subword predictions were aggregated into whole-word tags, more varied outcomes emerged. Spanish F1 increased from 0.79 to 0.82, largely thanks to a precision gain (0.74 to 0.80) alongside a modest recall uptick (0.82 to 0.83). English and Dutch saw smaller word-level gains (+0.01 and +0.03 F1, respectively), while Czech, Italian, and Romanian remained essentially unchanged (absolute variation around 0.01). These results underscore the importance of effective subword-to-word reconstructions, as even modest shifts in token-level behavior can translate into larger boundary-detection improvements—or regressions—at the word level.

Table 5: NER performance comparison (word level). All metrics are macro.

Language	F1 Score	F1 Score	Recall	Recall	Precision	Precision
	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Base Model	Pre-trained Model
English	0.73	0.74	0.74	0.79	0.71	0.70
Spanish	0.79	0.82	0.82	0.83	0.74	0.80
Swedish	0.74	0.75	0.76	0.78	0.72	0.72
Czech	0.75	0.75	0.78	0.79	0.73	0.73
Italian	0.72	0.72	0.75	0.75	0.69	0.70
Romanian	0.76	0.76	0.78	0.80	0.73	0.73
Dutch	0.74	0.77	0.76	0.79	0.73	0.76

In summary, cardiology-specific continuing pre-training produced clear perplexity reductions and token-level NER gains in languages where base models lacked specialized content (English, Spanish, Czech, Romanian). For languages whose checkpoints were already well suited to clinical text (Swedish, Italian, Dutch), perplexity sometimes increased, but NER performance remained stable or improved, particularly at the word level in Swedish and Spanish. The observed divergence between language-model fluency and downstream entity extraction highlights the need for further precision calibration and advanced aggregation strategies to fully leverage domain-adaptive gains across all languages.

It is important to note that the CardioCCC dataset was pre-annotated using the same base model as the one evaluated here. This may be one of the reasons why the baseline is stronger than in the rest of languages.

Table 6: Pre-training time per language

Language	English	Spanish	Swedish	Czech	Italian	Romanian	Dutch
Time (s)	8,242 (2.28)	67,738 (18.8h)	55,038 (15.2)	78,922 (21.9h)	40,533 (11.3h)	56,146 (15.6h)	54,010 (15.0)

Pre-training times generally scaled with corpus volume (Table 1) but displayed language-specific variability. English, with the smallest dataset (~942 M tokens), completed pre-training in approximately 2.3 hours. Spanish processed ~3.8 B tokens in 18.8 hours, while Swedish handled ~2.6 B tokens in 15.2 hours. The Czech model, covering ~2.9 B tokens (including 403 M general-domain words), required 21.9 hours, reflecting additional fragmentation from mixed corpora and language morphology. Italian (~4.8 B tokens) and Romanian (~4.4 B tokens) completed in 11.3 hours and 15.6 hours, respectively.

4 Qualitative Analysis

The central question driving the models' evaluation was whether the cardiology-adapted RoBERTa model not only “knows” the specialized vocabulary of ECG interpretation but also exhibits markedly higher confidence when that vocabulary appears in context. To test this, a canonical English description selected by one of BSC team doctors was selected from Paraclite: “His ECG showed normal sinus rhythm with subtle ST-segment depression in the inferior leads, and some Q waves.”

By masking the two-token phrases “sinus rhythm,” the base biomedical model was compared against the cardiology-adapted checkpoint. Although the base model did eventually surface “sinus rhythm” among its top candidates, it ranked the phrase outside the top ten and assigned it a joint probability of only ~0.02. In contrast, the adapted model placed “sinus rhythm” within its top seven predictions and boosted the joint probability to ~0.12—roughly a six-fold increase in confidence. This result suggests that domain-specific fine-tuning has sharpened the model’s certainty around core cardiology concepts.

Figure 5. Model qualitative assessment (English).

The experiment was then repeated in Spanish using the translated sentence:

“Su ECG mostró un ritmo sinusal normal con una sutil depresión del segmento ST en las derivaciones inferiores y algunas ondas Q.”

Here, the base Spanish biomedical model already demonstrated reasonable linguistic fluency and “ritmo sinusal” appeared within its top ten candidates with a nontrivial probability. Nonetheless, the cardiology-adapted Spanish model still increased its confidence in the correct two-token span by a factor of approximately 1.8. Notably, the relative lift in Spanish was smaller than in English, indicating that the original Spanish checkpoint may have enjoyed stronger cardiology coverage out of the box, but that domain adaptation continues to offer measurable gains.

Figure 6. Model qualitative assessment (Spanish).

To deepen the understanding of these effects, several follow-on analyses are proposed. First, it could be assembled a small masked-phrase benchmark of 50–100 real ECG reports, targeting both single- and multi-token cardiology terms (e.g. “atrial fibrillation,” “mitral regurgitation”) and computing top-k recovery rates, mean reciprocal rank, and probability-ratio improvements. Second, calibration curves will be generated for both base and adapted models to assess whether the adapted model predicted confidences better align with actual accuracy when recovering masked terms. Third, it is planned to perform an ablation study varying phrase length and word-distance (adjacent masks versus separated masks) to probe the model’s handling of long-range dependencies in ECG language. Finally, attention-weight and saliency analysis is planned to be performed to see if the cardiology-adapted model focuses more sharply on clinically informative tokens (e.g. “ECG,” “leads”) than the base model, and persistent failure cases—especially rarer terms like “fascicular block” or “pseudo-Q wave”—will be manually reviewed to guide further data collection and fine-tuning. Collectively, these steps will quantify not only whether but precisely how domain adaptation enhances masked-language modeling for cardiology.

5 Further Work

The resulting models are already a useful resource for cardiology related text representation that can be used for a wide variety of downstream tasks including NER and Entity Linking. In the next iteration, the plan is to improve the model training procedure by changing some optimizer hyperparameters to ensure a smooth and robust convergence to a minimum in the loss function.

To show a point of improvement in the models training, it can be seen in Figure 7 that the English model training curve converges to a local optimum, as evidenced by the loss plateau. By contrast, Figure 8 reveals that although both training and validation losses decrease appreciably—from 0.63 to 0.56—the curves do not stabilize; in particular, the training loss remains highly sensitive to the learning rate (see Figure 9). This instability likely stems from applying identical hyperparameters to every run: the chosen learning rate is appropriate for some languages (e.g., English and Spanish) but proves suboptimal for others. A straightforward remedy is to reduce the learning rate in those cases—by, for example, an order of magnitude.

Figure 7. Loss curves for English model CPT in evaluation (top) and training (below) sets.

Figure 8. Loss curves for Italian model CPT in evaluation (top) and training (below) sets.

Figure 9. Learning rate with warm-up and linear decay for the Italian model.

During this work, the main principles of transfer learning have been used as support. However, it can be worth studying what happens when the models are trained from scratch, i.e., using as initial weights random numbers instead of the results of previous model training.

In addition to this, some innovative architectures can be used in place of RoBERTa to explore if there is a substantial improvement when used. The most attractive candidate right now is ModernBERT³¹. ModernBERT is a modernized, encoder-only Transformer that extends the original BERT architecture by integrating a suite of recent advances—such as rotary positional embeddings for sequences up to 8,192 tokens, unpadding to skip redundant padding tokens, GeGLU feed-forward layers, and alternating attention—for both faster training and inference and improved downstream accuracy.

With the current work and the proposed improvements, the main goal is to build Language Models that can be a referent for automatic Information Extraction in the field of Medical NLP and, more specifically, in cardiology related environments.

31 Warner, B., Chaffin, A., Clavié, B., Weller, O., Hallström, O., Taghadouini, S., ... & Poli, I. (2024). Smarter, better, faster, longer: A modern bidirectional encoder for fast, memory efficient, and long context finetuning and inference. arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.13663.

ANNEX-I: Individual results of NER at token level evaluation for each language.

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.991918683052063	test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.9915398955345154
test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9991792440414429	test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9991161222726257
test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9917292594909668	test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9924237728118896
test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.9864890575408936	test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.9880042672157288
test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9758822917938232	test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9745564460754395
test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.9999368786811829	test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.9999368786811829
test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.985289454460144	test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.9859839677810669
test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.9628764390945435	test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.9632552266120911
test_accuracy_class_0	0.9378748536109924	test_accuracy_class_0	0.9425469040870667
test_accuracy_macro	0.9812418222427368	test_accuracy_macro	0.9819293022155762
test_accuracy_micro	0.9812418222427368	test_accuracy_micro	0.9819293022155762
test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8931552767753601	test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8888888955116272
test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.958730161198033	test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9556962251663208
test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9002285003662109	test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9104477763175964
test_f1_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.834876537322998	test_f1_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.8506289124488831
test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.8458434343338013	test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.8386062979698181
test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.8888888955116272	test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.8888888955116272
test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8516868352890015	test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8639705777168274
test_f1_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.8130959868431091	test_f1_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.8090550899505615
test_f1_class_0	0.9523440599441528	test_f1_class_0	0.955812394618988
test_f1_macro	0.8820943032397461	test_f1_macro	0.8846660852432251
test_f1_micro	0.9163695573806763	test_f1_micro	0.9192830920219421
test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.9083191752433777	test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.8978224396705627
test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9805194735527039	test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9741935729980469
test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9148606657981873	test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9063892960548401
test_precision_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.8310291767120361	test_precision_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.8628389239311218
test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.8618420958518982	test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.8477732539176941
test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	1.0	test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	1.0
test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8955823183059692	test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8725247383117676
test_precision_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.8188220262527466	test_precision_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.8422130942344666
test_precision_class_0	0.9512383937835693	test_precision_class_0	0.9572067856788635
test_precision_macro	0.9069125652313232	test_precision_macro	0.906773567199707
test_precision_micro	0.9210940003395081	test_precision_micro	0.9257810115814209
test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.8784893155097961	test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.8801313638687134
test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9378882050514221	test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9378882050514221
test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8860569596290588	test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9145427346229553
test_recall_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.8387596607208252	test_recall_class_B-SYMPATOM	0.8387596607208252
test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.830427885055542	test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.829635500907898
test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.800000011920929	test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.800000011920929
test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8118932247161865	test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8555825352668762
test_recall_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.8074495196342468	test_recall_class_I-SYMPATOM	0.7784090638160706
test_recall_class_0	0.9534522891044617	test_recall_class_0	0.9544220566749573
test_recall_macro	0.8604907989501953	test_recall_macro	0.865485668182373
test_recall_micro	0.9116933345794678	test_recall_micro	0.9128757119178772

Figure 10. Detailed NER results in Spanish using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.98196941614151	test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.9843975901603699
test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9979334473609924	test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9978301525115967
test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9842942952109741	test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9864124655723572
test_accuracy_class B-SYMPTOM	0.9799545407295227	test_accuracy_class B-SYMPTOM	0.9819177389144897
test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9682269096374512	test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9761314392089844
test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.9997933506965637	test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.9997933506965637
test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9771646857261658	test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9794378076686096
test_accuracy_class I-SYMPTOM	0.9549493789672852	test_accuracy_class I-SYMPTOM	0.957532525062561
test_accuracy_class 0	0.8942446708679199	test_accuracy_class 0	0.9130502343177795
test_accuracy_macro	0.9709478616714478	test_accuracy_macro	0.95753252506256186
test_accuracy_micro	0.9709478616714478	test_accuracy_micro	0.9751670360565186
test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.7862828969955444	test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.8266360759735107
test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.9413489699363708	test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.9387755393981934
test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8240740895271301	test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8519977331161499
test_f1_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7374830842018127	test_f1_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7727272510528564
test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.7996090054512024	test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.856521725654602
test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.7142857313156128	test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.7142857313156128
test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7805362343788147	test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.8050930500030518
test_f1_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7293606400489807	test_f1_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7565165758132935
test_f1_class 0	0.9186956286430359	test_f1_class 0	0.9314432144165039
test_f1_macro	0.803519606590271	test_f1_macro	0.82822185754776
test_f1_micro	0.870287299156189	test_f1_micro	0.8889231085777283
test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8617449402809143	test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8430913090705872
test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.9639639854431152	test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.9554896354675293
test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9001263976097107	test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.901190459728241
test_precision_class B-SYMPTOM	0.8158682584762573	test_precision_class B-SYMPTOM	0.8150684833526611
test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.875178337097168	test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.8879587650299072
test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	1.0	test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	1.0
test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.8952164053916931	test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9072847962379456
test_precision_class I-SYMPTOM	0.8131487965583801	test_precision_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7986241579055786
test_precision_class 0	0.8847154378890991	test_precision_class 0	0.9187560081481934
test_precision_macro	0.889995813369751	test_precision_macro	0.8919404149055481
test_precision_micro	0.87791508436203	test_precision_micro	0.8983807563781738
test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.7229729890823364	test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.8108108043670654
test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.9197707772254944	test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.922636091709137
test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7598719596862793	test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8078975677490234
test_recall_class B-SYMPTOM	0.6728395223617554	test_recall_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7345678806304932
test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.7360528111457825	test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.8272345662117004
test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.5555555820465088	test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.5555555820465088
test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.6919013857841492	test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7235915660858154
test_recall_class I-SYMPTOM	0.6612260890248108	test_recall_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7186269164085388
test_recall_class 0	0.9553903341283335	test_recall_class 0	0.9444857239723206
test_recall_macro	0.7417313456535339	test_recall_macro	0.7828229665756226
test_recall_micro	0.8627909421920776	test_recall_micro	0.879662573375549

Figure 11. Detailed NER results in English using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.9847680330276489	test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.9845320582389832
test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9973039694786072	test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9979974627494812
test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9967072701454163	test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9866252805709839
test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPOM	0.9789617657661436	test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPOM	0.9793530702599042
test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9681952595718754	test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9678614735603333
test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.998814582824707	test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.998849093914032
test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.9777706265449524	test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.9775347113609314
test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPOM	0.9569222927093506	test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPOM	0.9566805958747864
test_accuracy_class_0	0.8860737085342407	test_accuracy_class_0	0.8863844275474548
test_accuracy_macro	0.970657467842102	test_accuracy_macro	0.9706242680849622
test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8171834045678711	test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8053584008815918
test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9363940954208374	test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.943652868270874
test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8381446003913879	test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8437851667404175
test_f1_class_B-SYMPOM	0.7192012071609497	test_f1_class_B-SYMPOM	0.7169007658958435
test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.762795338630676	test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.7523171901702881
test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.7392485271530151	test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.721448481029163
test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7178850768996643	test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7201433777809143
test_f1_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6442015171051025	test_f1_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6469374299049377
test_f1_class_0	0.9183513522148132	test_f1_class_0	0.918321430683136
test_f1_macro	0.788153469525305	test_f1_macro	0.7854294776916504
test_f1_micro	0.8686338067054749	test_f1_micro	0.8679876327514648
test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.7828503251075745	test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.8073461055755615
test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9306803917617798	test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.925988698005676
test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8930976743833679	test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8127120641708937
test_precision_class_B-SYMPOM	0.720519153121915	test_precision_class_B-SYMPOM	0.7485582323475281
test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.7724941372871399	test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.7888031005859375
test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	0.735516369342804	test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	0.7092931009483337
test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7353380918502808	test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7236709594726562
test_precision_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6809002161026001	test_precision_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6738641858100891
test_precision_class_0	0.9198384284973145	test_precision_class_0	0.9226804375648499
test_precision_macro	0.7934008240699768	test_precision_macro	0.8031952362061635
test_precision_micro	0.8739404028141494	test_precision_micro	0.8761835293393716
test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.8546662926673889	test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.803380548954041
test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9422521591186523	test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9348732829093933
test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8236023187637329	test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.877306529388733
test_recall_class_B-SYMPOM	0.7088569402694702	test_recall_class_B-SYMPOM	0.687812267339783
test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.7533062100410461	test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.7190573215484619
test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.7430025339126587	test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.659333060073525
test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7012125486651916	test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.716650001352734
test_recall_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6112564286123352	test_recall_class_I-SYMPOM	0.6220799888478088
test_recall_class_0	0.9168691039085388	test_recall_class_0	0.914003721923828
test_recall_macro	0.783894772979736	test_recall_macro	0.7704662084579468
test_recall_micro	0.8639153838157654	test_recall_micro	0.8600206971168518

Figure 12. Detailed NER results in Italian using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

"epoch": 20.0,	"epoch": 20.0,
"eval_f1_B-DISEASE": 0.7817901762793086,	"eval_f1_B-DISEASE": 0.8039148351648352,
"eval_f1_B-MEDICATION": 0.9003636363636364,	"eval_f1_B-MEDICATION": 0.9135802469135802,
"eval_f1_B-PROCEDURE": 0.807497243666419,	"eval_f1_B-PROCEDURE": 0.8332962385933674,
"eval_f1_B-SYMPOM": 0.749749949089998,	"eval_f1_B-SYMPOM": 0.7587719298245614,
"eval_f1_I-DISEASE": 0.7814929524050312,	"eval_f1_I-DISEASE": 0.8072700204701941,
"eval_f1_I-MEDICATION": 0.8219862585883823,	"eval_f1_I-MEDICATION": 0.85840353127015,
"eval_f1_I-PROCEDURE": 0.76535504213698,	"eval_f1_I-PROCEDURE": 0.8042444208512258,
"eval_f1_I-SYMPOM": 0.748101219512195,	"eval_f1_I-SYMPOM": 0.754212153719947,
"eval_f1_0": 0.9340690618405233,	"eval_f1_0": 0.9397690537799345,
"eval_f1_macro": 0.8099750493155464,	"eval_f1_macro": 0.8304958254050512,
"eval_f1_micro": 0.8856842556201463,	"eval_f1_micro": 0.8954205393343494,
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"eval_precision_B-DISEASE": 0.7752885268160217,	"eval_precision_B-DISEASE": 0.7997950119576350,
"eval_precision_B-MEDICATION": 0.9849707602339181,	"eval_precision_B-MEDICATION": 0.916906269912536,
"eval_precision_B-PROCEDURE": 0.7895644674428633,	"eval_precision_B-PROCEDURE": 0.8221343873517787,
"eval_precision_B-SYMPOM": 0.7328901055924912,	"eval_precision_B-SYMPOM": 0.7393162393162394,
"eval_precision_I-DISEASE": 0.8128862590401051,	"eval_precision_I-DISEASE": 0.8231499051233396,
"eval_precision_I-MEDICATION": 0.8457583547557841,	"eval_precision_I-MEDICATION": 0.8609756097560975,
"eval_precision_I-PROCEDURE": 0.8085758039816233,	"eval_precision_I-PROCEDURE": 0.8589292692457992,
"eval_precision_I-SYMPOM": 0.7405493951612904,	"eval_precision_I-SYMPOM": 0.7433760417962433,
"eval_precision_0": 0.9318428106908232,	"eval_precision_0": 0.9385110952046085,
"eval_precision_macro": 0.8158140537471024,	"eval_precision_macro": 0.8336774645269328,
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"eval_rauc_macro": 0.8898271533381418,	"eval_rauc_macro": 0.9025490651748245,
"eval_rauc_micro": 0.9348833999438454,	"eval_rauc_micro": 0.940385631066698,
"eval_recall_B-DISEASE": 0.7884017949663037,	"eval_recall_B-DISEASE": 0.8080773213669313,
"eval_recall_B-MEDICATION": 0.8988031837916064,	"eval_recall_B-MEDICATION": 0.91027490382055,
"eval_recall_B-PROCEDURE": 0.826263579061372,	"eval_recall_B-PROCEDURE": 0.8447653429602888,
"eval_recall_B-SYMPOM": 0.767403764037674,	"eval_recall_B-SYMPOM": 0.7792792792792793,
"eval_recall_I-DISEASE": 0.7524342745861733,	"eval_recall_I-DISEASE": 0.7919912366114897,
"eval_recall_I-MEDICATION": 0.7995139732685298,	"eval_recall_I-MEDICATION": 0.8578371810449574,
"eval_recall_I-PROCEDURE": 0.7265221878224974,	"eval_recall_I-PROCEDURE": 0.7561059511523908,
"eval_recall_I-SYMPOM": 0.7526895491803278,	"eval_recall_I-SYMPOM": 0.7653688524590164,
"eval_recall_0": 0.9381163601912063,	"eval_recall_0": 0.9410363891502381,
"eval_recall_macro": 0.8052387365678388,	"eval_recall_macro": 0.828303908726825,
"eval_recall_micro": 0.8839713632295914,	"eval_recall_micro": 0.8937555931192205,
"eval_roc_auc_B-DISEASE": 0.8907712721485869,	"eval_roc_auc_B-DISEASE": 0.9010027687736512,
"eval_roc_auc_B-MEDICATION": 0.9475723712876061,	"eval_roc_auc_B-MEDICATION": 0.9548487807615482,
"eval_roc_auc_B-PROCEDURE": 0.9106213000921424,	"eval_roc_auc_B-PROCEDURE": 0.9202991881017119,
"eval_roc_auc_B-SYMPOM": 0.8801806670013568,	"eval_roc_auc_B-SYMPOM": 0.8803179690600589,
"eval_roc_auc_I-DISEASE": 0.868415903357308,	"eval_roc_auc_I-DISEASE": 0.88030595944063,
"eval_roc_auc_I-MEDICATION": 0.8991483809498878,	"eval_roc_auc_I-MEDICATION": 0.9283404151223205,
"eval_roc_auc_I-PROCEDURE": 0.8579189281972682,	"eval_roc_auc_I-PROCEDURE": 0.8741959319307016,
"eval_roc_auc_I-SYMPOM": 0.8651058143168044,	"eval_roc_auc_I-SYMPOM": 0.8714236321333738,
"eval_roc_auc_0": 0.8887112426924548,	"eval_roc_auc_0": 0.8983206137956482,
"eval_runtime": 4.5529,	"eval_runtime": 3.584,
"eval_samples_per_second": 113.334,	"eval_samples_per_second": 143.974,
"eval_steps_per_second": 7.248,	"eval_steps_per_second": 9.208,

Figure 13. Detailed NER results in Dutch using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.9855623841285796	test_accuracy_class_B-DISEASE	0.9867095348285566
test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9976499888657959	test_accuracy_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9982717837280928
test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9858047366142273	test_accuracy_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.9851197680364685
test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.9762885570526123	test_accuracy_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.9774793982505798
test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9646120871411133	test_accuracy_class_I-DISEASE	0.9683426822529682
test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.9995152354240417	test_accuracy_class_I-MEDICATION	0.9994625409186683
test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.9773635263211365	test_accuracy_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.9782883654678715
test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.9467872486877441	test_accuracy_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.9477984279868360
test_accuracy_class_0	0.8896628618240356	test_accuracy_class_0	0.8977668881416321
test_accuracy_macro	0.9692407250484358	test_accuracy_macro	0.9710147380828857
test_accuracy_micro	0.9692407250484358	test_accuracy_micro	0.971014678478241
test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8637358546257819	test_f1_class_B-DISEASE	0.8805158389671326
test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9315741062164307	test_f1_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9503632187843323
test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8526346584756165	test_f1_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.856252722876416
test_f1_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.7269417643597858	test_f1_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.7579967432403564
test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.8834648299217224	test_f1_class_I-DISEASE	0.8355054259380232
test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.781298713684882	test_f1_class_I-MEDICATION	0.6832298048390815
test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7989692525863647	test_f1_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.806895911693573
test_f1_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.6554473842488898	test_f1_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.6924126148223877
test_f1_class_0	0.9128123982429584	test_f1_class_0	0.9156838859425354
test_f1_macro	0.8043428910835266	test_f1_macro	0.819798469543457
test_f1_micro	0.863141655921936	test_f1_micro	0.8715798854827881
test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.9755797743797382	test_precision_class_B-DISEASE	0.8505578637123188
test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9448298676490784	test_precision_class_B-MEDICATION	0.949788273888289
test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8821019530296326	test_precision_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8318891638935669
test_precision_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.7653973698616828	test_precision_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.743225216865396
test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.84480728187561835	test_precision_class_I-DISEASE	0.819617589841919
test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	0.75	test_precision_class_I-MEDICATION	0.6962825165557861
test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8119879961813794	test_precision_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7971121668815613
test_precision_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.715773808710782	test_precision_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.681888513931274
test_precision_class_0	0.8998928186804286	test_precision_class_0	0.9337741136585893
test_precision_macro	0.8320839518726929	test_precision_macro	0.811696585744934
test_precision_micro	0.8708885878372192	test_precision_micro	0.8717565746397373
test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.8522080183829175	test_recall_class_B-DISEASE	0.9126594662666321
test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9194427728652954	test_recall_class_B-MEDICATION	0.9589388268389282
test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8269473910331726	test_recall_class_B-PROCEDURE	0.8888428896530151
test_recall_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.6921658039651489	test_recall_class_B-SYMPPTOM	0.7752848180397034
test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.7665847839891733	test_recall_class_I-DISEASE	0.850214857647798
test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.6585366129875183	test_recall_class_I-MEDICATION	0.678731723885632
test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.7710111737251282	test_recall_class_I-PROCEDURE	0.8169227838516235
test_recall_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.6044991612434387	test_recall_class_I-SYMPPTOM	0.7818976887594299
test_recall_class_0	0.9253894792366828	test_recall_class_0	0.8982818974121094
test_recall_macro	0.7796338796615691	test_recall_macro	0.8286198973655701
test_recall_micro	0.8563822587858276	test_recall_micro	0.868426203727222

Figure 14. Detailed NER results in Romanian using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.9769102334976196	test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.9777911901473999
test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9969862699508667	test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9966617226600647
test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9755192995071411	test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9770957231521606
test_accuracy_class B-SYMPOM	0.9727837443351746	test_accuracy_class B-SYMPOM	0.9736183285713196
test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9671735763549805	test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9706645985218663
test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.999026358127594	test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.999026358127594
test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9720419049263	test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9732474088668823
test_accuracy_class I-SYMPOM	0.952614963054657	test_accuracy_class I-SYMPOM	0.9561851024627686
test_accuracy_class 0	0.8934532403945923	test_accuracy_class 0	0.9014280438423157
test_accuracy_macro	0.9673899412155151	test_accuracy_macro	0.9695175886154175
test_accuracy_micro	0.9673899412155151	test_accuracy_micro	0.9695175886154175
test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.8248944878578186	test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.8276358246803284
test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.9374398589134216	test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.930367529392424
test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7869249582290649	test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7970418930053711
test_f1_class B-SYMPOM	0.7496801614761353	test_f1_class B-SYMPOM	0.7458686828613281
test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.8273170590400696	test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.8395748734474182
test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.8205128312110901	test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.8037382960319519
test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7381675839424133	test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7425256371498108
test_f1_class I-SYMPOM	0.7096590995788574	test_f1_class I-SYMPOM	0.7224669456481934
test_f1_class 0	0.9073984622955322	test_f1_class 0	0.91525282883834839
test_f1_macro	0.8113327026367188	test_f1_macro	0.8138308525085449
test_f1_micro	0.85468989610672	test_f1_micro	0.8632824420928955
test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8162839412689209	test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8381924033164978
test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.9643564224243164	test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.9620000123977661
test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7946210503578186	test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8199492692947388
test_precision_class B-SYMPOM	0.7430261969566345	test_precision_class B-SYMPOM	0.7753017544746399
test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.807619035243988	test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.849897563457489
test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	0.9056603908538818	test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	1.0
test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.752212405204773	test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.779026210308075
test_precision_class I-SYMPOM	0.6629511713981628	test_precision_class I-SYMPOM	0.6953080892562866
test_precision_class 0	0.929420530796051	test_precision_class 0	0.9269336462020874
test_precision_macro	0.8195723295211792	test_precision_macro	0.8496232032775879
test_precision_micro	0.8605371713638306	test_precision_micro	0.874988317489624
test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.8336886763572693	test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.8173418641090393
test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.9119850397109985	test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.9007490873336792
test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7793765068054199	test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7753797173500061
test_recall_class B-SYMPOM	0.7564544081687927	test_recall_class B-SYMPOM	0.718588650226593
test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.847999989864197	test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.8295000195503235
test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.75	test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.671875
test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7246376872062683	test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7092924118041992
test_recall_class I-SYMPOM	0.7634474039077759	test_recall_class I-SYMPOM	0.7518337368965149
test_recall_class 0	0.8863958716392517	test_recall_class 0	0.9038733839988708
test_recall_macro	0.8059983849525452	test_recall_macro	0.786492645740509
test_recall_micro	0.848921537399292	test_recall_micro	0.8518856167793274

Figure 15. Detailed NER results in Czech using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.9796023964881897	test_accuracy_class B-DISEASE	0.9817693829536438
test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9967966675758362	test_accuracy_class B-MEDICATION	0.9974561929702759
test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9756925106048584	test_accuracy_class B-PROCEDURE	0.9779665251350403
test_accuracy_class B-SYMPTOM	0.9771057367324829	test_accuracy_class B-SYMPTOM	0.9787673731422424
test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9735255241394043	test_accuracy_class I-DISEASE	0.9774825572967529
test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.9993404746055603	test_accuracy_class I-MEDICATION	0.9992933869361877
test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9765404462814331	test_accuracy_class I-PROCEDURE	0.9778123497962952
test_accuracy_class I-SYMPTOM	0.9592990279197693	test_accuracy_class I-SYMPTOM	0.9649990797042847
test_accuracy_class 0	0.9203410744667053	test_accuracy_class 0	0.9204823970794678
test_accuracy_macro	0.9731382131576538	test_accuracy_macro	0.9751010537147522
test_accuracy_micro	0.9731382131576538	test_accuracy_micro	0.9751009941101074
test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.8190555572509766	test_f1_class B-DISEASE	0.8401486873626789
test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.9014492630958557	test_f1_class B-MEDICATION	0.9179331064224243
test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.809312641620636	test_f1_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8266173601150513
test_f1_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7883275151252747	test_f1_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7992895245552063
test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.831129789352417	test_f1_class I-DISEASE	0.8512756824493408
test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.3636363744735718	test_f1_class I-MEDICATION	0.4000000059604645
test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7440904378890991	test_f1_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7532739639282227
test_f1_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7548240423202515	test_f1_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7864328622817993
test_f1_class 0	0.9335638284683228	test_f1_class 0	0.9346243143081665
test_f1_macro	0.7717099189758301	test_f1_macro	0.7899556199508667
test_f1_micro	0.8788422346115112	test_f1_micro	0.8880258202552795
test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8588957190513611	test_precision_class B-DISEASE	0.8699743151664734
test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.8988439440727234	test_precision_class B-MEDICATION	0.9617834687232971
test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8481796979904175	test_precision_class B-PROCEDURE	0.8666666746139526
test_precision_class B-SYMPTOM	0.8131176829338074	test_precision_class B-SYMPTOM	0.84190833568573
test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.8232142925262451	test_precision_class I-DISEASE	0.873563230076892
test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	0.66666666865348816	test_precision_class I-MEDICATION	0.5555555820465088
test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7751606106758118	test_precision_class I-PROCEDURE	0.8015607595443726
test_precision_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7648073434829712	test_precision_class I-SYMPTOM	0.8075566927391052
test_precision_class 0	0.9431610703468323	test_precision_class 0	0.9307312369346619
test_precision_macro	0.8213385343551636	test_precision_macro	0.8343666195869446
test_precision_micro	0.8928382992744446	test_precision_micro	0.8994373679161072
test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.7827476263046265	test_recall_class B-DISEASE	0.8123003244408024
test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.9040697813034058	test_recall_class B-MEDICATION	0.8779069781303406
test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7738515734672546	test_recall_class B-PROCEDURE	0.7901859985160828
test_recall_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7650042176246643	test_recall_class B-SYMPTOM	0.7607777118682861
test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.8391990065574646	test_recall_class I-DISEASE	0.8300970792770386
test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.25	test_recall_class I-MEDICATION	0.3125
test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7154150009155273	test_recall_class I-PROCEDURE	0.7104743123054504
test_recall_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7450980544090271	test_recall_class I-SYMPTOM	0.7663865685462952
test_recall_class 0	0.9241599440574646	test_recall_class 0	0.9385501146316528
test_recall_macro	0.7443939447402954	test_recall_macro	0.755455493927002
test_recall_micro	0.8652782440185547	test_recall_micro	0.8769001960754395

Figure 16. Detailed NER results in Swedish using token level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

ANNEX-II: Individual results of NER at word level evaluation for each language

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7895247340202332	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7855044007301331
test_DISEASE_precision	0.762172281742096	test_DISEASE_precision	0.7652671933174133
test_DISEASE_recall	0.818913459777832	test_DISEASE_recall	0.8068410754203796
test_DISEASE_support	497.0	test_DISEASE_support	497.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8207171559333801	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.9130434989929199
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.7686567306518555	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.9292035102844238
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8803418874740601	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8974359035491943
test_MEDICATION_support	117.0	test_MEDICATION_support	117.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7759914398193359	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.8138527870178223
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7494823932647705	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7932489514350891
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.804444432258606	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.835555534362793
test_PROCEDURE_support	450.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	450.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.7252747416496277	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.7483629584312439
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6863085031509399	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.7220216393470764
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.768932044506073	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7766990065574646
test_SYMPTOM_support	515.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	515.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7778770327568054	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.8151909112930298
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7416549921035767	test_macro_avg_precision	0.8024353384971619
test_macro_avg_recall	0.818157970905304	test_macro_avg_recall	0.8291328549385071
test_macro_avg_support	1579.0	test_macro_avg_support	1579.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7668581604957581	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7903822660446167
test_micro_avg_precision	0.7337962985038757	test_micro_avg_precision	0.7699699401855469
test_micro_avg_recall	0.8030399084091187	test_micro_avg_recall	0.8119062781333923
test_micro_avg_support	1579.0	test_micro_avg_support	1579.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7670236229896545	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.790919840335846
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.7342928647994995	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.7712842226028442
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.8030399084091187	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.8119062781333923
test_weighted_avg_support	1579.0	test_weighted_avg_support	1579.0

Figure 17. Detailed NER results in Spanish using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.6781116127967834	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7082096934318542
test_DISEASE_precision	0.6638655662536621	test_DISEASE_precision	0.6450450420379639
test_DISEASE_recall	0.6929824352264404	test_DISEASE_recall	0.7850877046585083
test_DISEASE_support	456.0	test_DISEASE_support	456.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8888888955116272	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.886956512928009
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.900900003639221	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8793103694915771
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8771929740905762	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8947368264198303
test_MEDICATION_support	114.0	test_MEDICATION_support	114.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.6899999976158142	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.6948356628417969
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7022900581359863	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.6651685237884521
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.6781326532363892	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7272727489471436
test_PROCEDURE_support	407.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	407.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6452261209487915	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6612740159034729
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5846994519233704	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6022099256515503
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7197309136390686	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7331838607780806
test_SYMPTOM_support	446.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	446.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7255566716194153	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7378189563751221
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7129390239715576	test_macro_avg_precision	0.6979334950447083
test_macro_avg_recall	0.7420097589492798	test_macro_avg_recall	0.7850703001022339
test_macro_avg_support	1423.0	test_macro_avg_support	1423.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.6863143444061279	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.702790379524231
test_micro_avg_precision	0.6625245213508606	test_micro_avg_precision	0.6528028845787048
test_micro_avg_recall	0.7118763327598572	test_micro_avg_recall	0.7610681653022766
test_micro_avg_support	1423.0	test_micro_avg_support	1423.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.6880906820297241	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7039936780929565
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.669032633304596	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6561427712440491
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7118763327598572	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7610681653022766
test_weighted_avg_support	1423.0	test_weighted_avg_support	1423.0

Figure 18. Detailed NER results in English using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.6763816475868225	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7119109630584717
test_DISEASE_precision	0.6487341523170471	test_DISEASE_precision	0.6823808550834656
test_DISEASE_recall	0.7064905166625977	test_DISEASE_recall	0.7441125512123108
test_DISEASE_support	3482.0	test_DISEASE_support	3482.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.9143199324607849	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.9284425973892212
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.917067289352417	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.9346246719360352
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9115890264511108	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9223417043685913
test_MEDICATION_support	837.0	test_MEDICATION_support	837.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7409454584121704	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7681159377098083
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.731056272983551	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7552009224891663
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7511058449745178	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7814803719520569
test_PROCEDURE_support	3391.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	3391.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.646364688873291	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6801071763038635
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6250306963920593	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6611262559890747
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.6692065000534058	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7002102136611938
test_SYMPTOM_support	3806.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	3806.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7445029020309448	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7721441984176636
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7304720878601074	test_macro_avg_precision	0.7583332061767578
test_macro_avg_recall	0.7595979571342468	test_macro_avg_recall	0.7870362401008606
test_macro_avg_support	11516.0	test_macro_avg_support	11516.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7018861770629883	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.732970118522644
test_micro_avg_precision	0.6826725602149963	test_micro_avg_precision	0.7134752869606018
test_micro_avg_recall	0.722212553024292	test_micro_avg_recall	0.7535602450370789
test_micro_avg_support	11516.0	test_micro_avg_support	11516.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7027662992477417	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7336878776550293
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6846436262130737	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.7151322960853577
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.722212553024292	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7535602450370789
test_weighted_avg_support	11516.0	test_weighted_avg_support	11516.0

Figure 19. Detailed NER results in Dutch using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.727979302406311	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7400215864181519
test_DISEASE_precision	0.6784162521362305	test_DISEASE_precision	0.7149556875228882
test_DISEASE_recall	0.7853549718856812	test_DISEASE_recall	0.7669088840484619
test_DISEASE_support	1789.0	test_DISEASE_support	1789.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.9324324131011963	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.9470124244689941
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.9118942618370056	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.9292035102844238
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9539170265197754	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9655172228813171
test_MEDICATION_support	434.0	test_MEDICATION_support	435.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7541173100471497	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7585052847862244
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7495692372322083	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7288317084312439
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7587209343910217	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7906976938247681
test_PROCEDURE_support	1720.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	1720.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6257501244544983	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6330321431159973
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6088110208511353	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5726612210273743
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.6436588168144226	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7076318860054016
test_SYMPTOM_support	1782.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	1782.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7600697875022888	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7696428298950195
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7371726632118225	test_macro_avg_precision	0.7364130616188049
test_macro_avg_recall	0.7854129076004028	test_macro_avg_recall	0.8076888918876648
test_macro_avg_support	5725.0	test_macro_avg_support	5726.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7193263173103333	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7255240678787231
test_micro_avg_precision	0.694471538066864	test_micro_avg_precision	0.6853548884391785
test_micro_avg_recall	0.7460262179374695	test_micro_avg_recall	0.7706950902938843
test_micro_avg_support	5725.0	test_micro_avg_support	5726.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7195107340812683	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7280023097991943
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6958268880844116	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6911163330078125
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7460262179374695	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7706950902938843
test_weighted_avg_support	5725.0	test_weighted_avg_support	5726.0

Figure 20. Detailed NER results in Romanian using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.6451094150543213	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.6473708152770996
test_DISEASE_precision	0.6257802844047546	test_DISEASE_precision	0.5954837203025818
test_DISEASE_recall	0.66567063331604	test_DISEASE_recall	0.70916333677482605
test_DISEASE_support	3012.0	test_DISEASE_support	3012.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8997696042060852	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8986526131629944
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8854875564575195	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8991793394088745
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9145199060440063	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.898126482963562
test_MEDICATION_support	854.0	test_MEDICATION_support	854.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7238339185714722	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7300015687942505
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.6888346672058105	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.692307710647583
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7625802159309387	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7720364928245544
test_PROCEDURE_support	2961.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	2961.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6001172661781311	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.5894705653190613
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5536921620368958	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5479791164398193
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.6550400257110596	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.6377599835395813
test_SYMPTOM_support	3125.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	3125.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7172075510025024	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7163739204406738
test_macro_avg_precision	0.6884486675262451	test_macro_avg_precision	0.6837374567985535
test_macro_avg_recall	0.7494527101516724	test_macro_avg_recall	0.7542715668678284
test_macro_avg_support	9952.0	test_macro_avg_support	9952.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.6749155521392822	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.6733861565589905
test_micro_avg_precision	0.6410812735557556	test_micro_avg_precision	0.6311626434326172
test_micro_avg_recall	0.7125201225280762	test_micro_avg_recall	0.7216640114784241
test_micro_avg_support	9952.0	test_micro_avg_support	9952.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.6762571930885315	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.6753376722335815
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6441904902458191	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6354354619979858
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7125201225280762	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7216640114784241
test_weighted_avg_support	9952.0	test_weighted_avg_support	9952.0

Figure 21. Detailed NER results in Italian using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7470119595527649	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7534517049789429
test_DISEASE_precision	0.7183908224105835	test_DISEASE_precision	0.7180451154708862
test_DISEASE_recall	0.7780082821846008	test_DISEASE_recall	0.7925311326980591
test_DISEASE_support	482.0	test_DISEASE_support	482.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8669527769088745	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8583333492279053
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8632478713989258	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8306451439857483
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8706896305084229	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8879310488700867
test_MEDICATION_support	116.0	test_MEDICATION_support	116.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7324262857437134	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7488372325897217
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.717777886390686	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7523364424705505
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7476851940155029	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7453703880310059
test_PROCEDURE_support	432.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	432.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6673346757888794	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6586345434188843
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6132596731185913	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.6062846779823303
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7318681478500366	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7208791375160217
test_SYMPTOM_support	455.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	455.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7534314393997192	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7548142075538635
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7281690239906311	test_macro_avg_precision	0.72682785987854
test_macro_avg_recall	0.782062828540802	test_macro_avg_recall	0.786677896976471
test_macro_avg_support	1485.0	test_macro_avg_support	1485.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.726339398146057	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.729903519153595
test_micro_avg_precision	0.6936274766921997	test_micro_avg_precision	0.6984615325927734
test_micro_avg_recall	0.7622895836830139	test_micro_avg_recall	0.7643097639083862
test_micro_avg_support	1485.0	test_micro_avg_support	1485.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.727725088596344	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7312503457069397
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6973159909248352	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.7025733590126038
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7622895836830139	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7643097639083862
test_weighted_avg_support	1485.0	test_weighted_avg_support	1485.0

Figure 22. Detailed NER results in Czech using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).

Test metric	DataLoader 0	Test metric	DataLoader 0
test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7020407915115356	test_DISEASE_f1-score	0.7039674520492554
test_DISEASE_precision	0.6745098233222961	test_DISEASE_precision	0.6744639277458191
test_DISEASE_recall	0.7319148778915405	test_DISEASE_recall	0.73617023229599
test_DISEASE_support	470.0	test_DISEASE_support	470.0
test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.8888888955116272	test_MEDICATION_f1-score	0.886956512928009
test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8666666746139526	test_MEDICATION_precision	0.8793103694915771
test_MEDICATION_recall	0.9122806787490845	test_MEDICATION_recall	0.8947368264198303
test_MEDICATION_support	114.0	test_MEDICATION_support	114.0
test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7336561679840088	test_PROCEDURE_f1-score	0.7367178201675415
test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7444717288017273	test_PROCEDURE_precision	0.7289719581604004
test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.723150372505188	test_PROCEDURE_recall	0.7446300983428955
test_PROCEDURE_support	419.0	test_PROCEDURE_support	419.0
test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6315789222717285	test_SYMPTOM_f1-score	0.6524685621261597
test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5920303463935852	test_SYMPTOM_precision	0.5891608595848083
test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.6767895817756653	test_SYMPTOM_recall	0.7310194969177246
test_SYMPTOM_support	461.0	test_SYMPTOM_support	461.0
test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7390412092208862	test_macro_avg_f1-score	0.7450276017189026
test_macro_avg_precision	0.7194196581840515	test_macro_avg_precision	0.7179767489433289
test_macro_avg_recall	0.7610338926315308	test_macro_avg_recall	0.7766391634941101
test_macro_avg_support	1464.0	test_macro_avg_support	1464.0
test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.7021136283874512	test_micro_avg_f1-score	0.709343671798706
test_micro_avg_precision	0.6796675324440002	test_micro_avg_precision	0.6734192967414856
test_micro_avg_recall	0.7260928750038147	test_micro_avg_recall	0.749316930770874
test_micro_avg_support	1464.0	test_micro_avg_support	1464.0
test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7034510374069214	test_weighted_avg_f1-score	0.7113732695579529
test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6835240721702576	test_weighted_avg_precision	0.6791542768478394
test_weighted_avg_recall	0.7260928750038147	test_weighted_avg_recall	0.749316930770874
test_weighted_avg_support	1464.0	test_weighted_avg_support	1464.0

Figure 23. Detailed NER results in Swedish using word level evaluation before (left) and after pre-training (right).